

Analysis of Changes in Speaking Manners by Mixing Indonesian and English: A Case Study of Generation Z Teenagers

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to examine the actual situation of social phenomena that occur among young people, using Indonesian and English. Today's children, better known as Generation Z, have experienced many significant changes in their increasingly advanced modern evolution. One of these is the communication style of Gen Z children, who are accustomed to using multiple languages. In Indonesia, it is common for everyone to use Indonesian for communication. However, it is very unfortunate that over time, changes have occurred in language styles in society, especially among young people. Today's children, better known as Generation Z, have experienced many significant changes in their increasingly advanced modern evolution. One of these is the communication style of Gen Z children, who are accustomed to using multiple languages. In Indonesia, it is common for everyone to use Indonesian for communication. However, it is very unfortunate that over time, changes have occurred in language styles in society, especially among young people.

INTRODUCTION

Language is literally a system of sounds produced by the human articulation apparatus. The term sound system, can be interpreted as the result of air vibrations, can be captured by the sense of hearing, or sounds produced by the communication process. Language sounds can be studied phonetically. In everyday life, humans are never separated from the use of language. With language, humans can communicate with one another, and convey ideas, and others. Indonesian is a unified language used by all Indonesian people in everyday life (Rachman, Ryan, et al., 2021). According to Sudaryanto (1993) language is basically a tool or means for communication between humans. Language is also one of the characteristics that distinguish humans from other creatures. This is because humans have the ability to think and the ability to develop their minds. With this ability, humans develop a tool to communicate, to express their thoughts, feelings, or desires, namely language. However, city dwellers are more likely to use good and correct Indonesian in their daily lives or even mix it with foreign languages.

This language-mixing phenomenon is often referred to as "Jaksel language". In its development, this language was often used by young people in the South Jakarta area. But now it has spread throughout Indonesia. One of the characteristics of this language is the mixture of Indonesian and English in its use, then has abbreviated words and sometimes uses reversed language. The use of this unique language is very much in demand by young people. The use of Indonesian is now starting to shift, replaced by the use of teenage language known as slang. Slang interference sometimes appears in the use of Indonesian in official situations which results in the use of bad and incorrect language. The users of this slang mostly come from Generation Z. Generation Z commonly referred to as *Anak zaman Now* is the current generation of young people who have an age of around 10 years to 24 years. Generation Z children live in modern times where everything is instant and facilitated by technology. Therefore, they are quicker to learn new things. This generation is a very creative generation, one of which is evidenced by the continued development of the language they use when socializing. New words with various forms emerge because of the modification process they do. Therefore, the social language of this generation is more unique and distinctive, which is commonly referred to as Generation Z slang.

Language development is inseparable from the social changes that occur in society. In other words, social change will affect the forms of language used. This is inseparable from the nature of language which is a social phenomenon. Therefore, language will not be static. The changes that occur are not only due to dissatisfaction with the existing language, but also more likely to look for something new that is different from what exists at that time. Teenagers, as a new generation of language users, have their own creativity in communicating, both among teenagers and with people who are older or younger in age. Many new terms appear in communication. Sometimes they use new terms developed from the old vocabulary they have.

Poedjosoedarmo (2009) states that there are two kinds of language change processes, namely internal changes that occur due to the grammatical system and external changes caused by the influence of other languages. Therefore, this mixed language phenomenon occurs because of the influence of English in their lives. The rise of the use of mixed language between Indonesian and English is due to a lack of love for the national language. Words such as "literally, which is, even, to be honest, basically, usually, prefer, confuse, sceptical" and the like are now often found in various social media networks, such as Twitter and Instagram columns. Social media as a means of communicating from various parts of Indonesia and even the world is one of the communication tools that are often used. According to Nugroho (2021), there are various points of view regarding the use of language by South Jakarta children. The positive side of using this language is that it indirectly makes users practice English in their daily communication even though it is not in 1 complete sentence. So this is one alternative for teenagers to be literate in foreign languages, especially English. Crystal (2000) states that English is a global language. This statement represents the meaning that English is used by various nations to communicate.

Changes in the way of speaking with mixed Indonesian and English in Gen Z will cause grammatical rules, and the spelling of Indonesian to change, if it happens in the long run it will have a considerable impact on the development of the Indonesian language. Sometimes individuals mix languages but not according to their portions. So that other individuals who read it will misinterpret the composition of the words. The purpose of this study is that the author wants to analyze changes in the manner of speaking with mixed languages in Gen Z, and whether the use of mixed languages has an impact on the development of the Indonesian language. Writing about the manner of speaking by mixing Indonesian and English uses a qualitative descriptive study type of writing by using the interview method.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Language Procedures

According to Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 63 of 2019 concerning the Use of Indonesian Language, it is said that the use of Indonesian must meet the criteria of good and correct Indonesian, namely Indonesian which is used in accordance with the language context and in harmony with the social values of the community which is in accordance with the rules of Indonesian Language which are grammar rules, spelling rules and rules for forming terms.

Indonesians must be prioritized as a national identity, unifying diversity so as to form a young generation of Indonesians who are aware of the great role of the Indonesian language, and Indonesians must be able to compete as a self-identity in the younger generation in the global world. The use of foreign languages can shift the use of the State Language in the public sphere if its use is not disciplined. For this reason, an orderly attitude to language is needed.

Generation Z

Youarti and Hidayah (2018) suggest that Generation Z is a generation associated with smartphones and is categorized as the generation born from 1998 to 2009. Generation Z is often referred to as the internet generation because everything they do is connected to social media.

Behaviour Teenagers

Adolescence is a time when children undergo personal transition and psychological development toward adulthood. In general, many types of changes occur during adolescence: physical, biological, mental, emotional, and psychosocial. The various changes that occur during adolescence can affect a person's personal life, family environment, and society. When it comes to shortcuts to preventing teens from getting into the wrong relationships and developing deviant behavior, the easiest way is to take a restrictive or even repressive approach. Banning teenagers from going out or forcing them to continue studying in their textbooks may seem effective in the short term. However, to further ensure the continuation and growth of teenagers' consciousness of autonomously maintaining honor and moral ethics, the tactical steps that are really needed are It's a way to meet the needs of young people. A desire for healthy connections and intimacy with the opposite sex without abandoning the moral norms and ethics enforced in society. Effective coaching and mentoring models for working with adolescent teenagers. In addition to the possibility of offering a variety of interesting alternative activities, the developed approach also relies on adolescent relationship patterns, which generally favor egalitarian interactions, to ensure that teenagers are contextually and truly Equally important is how we understand our lifestyles. Emotional changes began during the "Despite II" period. During this period, children begin to demonstrate a sense of "I" through actions they believe are right, even if in reality those actions are rather negative. Also at this time, they experience an imbalance, an emotional imbalance, which makes their emotions capricious, capricious, and insecure. Commonly observed behaviors include: They have low self-esteem, withdrawing from their environment, feel incompetent and useless, remaining silent (passive), becoming rebellious, wanting to win alone, and sometimes becoming aggressive. At this stage of adolescence, manifestations of angry feelings can occur in the form of aggressive behavior, both verbal (contradictions, quarrels) and physical (hitting, fighting). In line with previous research: (Smith-Hefner, 2009); (Bloom & Reenen, 2013); (Yusra, 2020); (Muin et al., 2021); (Tamalawe et al., 2022); (Tarihoran et al., 2022).

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a qualitative case study method with Generation Z research subjects who use social media. In the case study method, data collection methods are used using interview techniques. Qualitative analysis uses subjective assessment which is used as a tool in analyzing the value or

development of research subjects based on information that cannot be measured. The purpose of this research is to analyze changes in the manner of speaking with mixed language in Gen Z, and whether the use of mixed language has an impact on the development of Indonesian. In this study, interviews will be conducted with 19 respondents to answer questions about the use of mixed language.

The interviews conducted in this study used structured interviews with a list of questions that had been prepared, including: (1). Do you know the phenomenon of using mixed Indonesian and English in speaking to teenagers today? (2). Are you one of the teenagers who also use mixed language? (3) How do you respond to this phenomenon? (4) Do you think mixed language will damage the Indonesian language? (5) What is your opinion regarding the slogan prioritize Indonesian, preserve regional languages, and master foreign languages? (6) How do you think teenagers should respond to the mixed language phenomenon?

RESEARCH RESULT

In this discussion, it will be described what are the changes in the procedure for speaking with mixed languages in Gen Z. The results of this discussion are motivated by the rampant phenomenon of using mixed languages that we encounter a lot on social media which is then researched from this phenomenon. From the results of interviews conducted with 19 respondents, it was found that all respondents knew about the phenomenon of mixed language use in Gen Z. Of the 19 respondents, 18 respondents used mixed language. Of the 19 respondents, 18 respondents used mixed language and 1 respondent did not use mixed language because the respondent felt that the use of mixed language was ineffective and feared that the interlocutor did not understand what the respondent meant. This is in line with the Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 63 of 2019 concerning the Use of the Indonesian Language, which states that the use of Indonesian must meet the criteria of good and correct Indonesian, namely Indonesian language that is used in accordance with the language context and in harmony with the social values of the community which is in accordance with the rules of Indonesian language which are grammar rules, spelling rules and rules for forming terms. Based on interviews that have been conducted with respondents, the results show that some respondents have reasons for using mixed languages such as the use of mixed languages can help in practicing developing skills in speaking foreign languages, although sometimes there are still mistakes in pronunciation or grammar, but it is also an exercise in developing foreign languages, over time the teenagers will be more honed and trained in using these foreign languages. If this continues for a long period of time, there will be concerns about the increasingly prevalent use of mixed languages on social media. Mixed language is considered a serious threat to the rules of Indonesian grammar, because although in the world of linguistics it is known as standard and non-standard language, mixed language is non-standard language that does not heed. This will also cause the level of understanding of Indonesian to be

disrupted (Eliastuti, et al, 2023). The existence of globalization is a factor in the use of mixed languages, language development becomes a natural thing but can reduce the existence of Indonesian. In the development of the times, the large population must be supported by increasingly proficient technology, the community has consciously or unconsciously shifted words in communicating in everyday life.

Respondents' opinions on the slogan applied by the Indonesian government "prioritize Indonesian, preserve regional languages, and master foreign languages" one of them is to prioritize Indonesian, meaning that Indonesian is used as communication in everyday life, in formal and non-formal situations. Indonesian is used by us as Indonesians to communicate with people between cities or islands in Indonesia. Moreover, Indonesia is a vast country, and there are many tribes. So Indonesian is used as the main language in communication between tribes. Simply put, Sundanese people speak to Javanese people, of course there will be language differences between the two, for this reason Indonesian is used as a unifying language. Preserve regional languages, do not let a language become extinct because people who know the language no longer exist. We can also learn local languages as a form of our love for Indonesia which has a variety of languages. Master foreign languages, we also need to master at least 1 foreign language, generally an international language, namely English.

This is related to the ease with which information is obtained in this era of globalization. Even if we don't master it, at least we understand what is being said and can pronounce it. This is so that we are not easily lied to or cheated with fake news from outside. Mastering a foreign language is also necessary so that we can help foreigners who are in Indonesia, or when we are abroad. This can also be useful in the world of work where now there are many jobs that require English or foreign language skills. From the answers of 18 respondents who use mixed language in daily conversation, they do not know that this slogan has been implemented by the Indonesian government so they still use mixed language in daily conversation.

There is actually no problem with mixed language, just understand the context or situation. In order not to look "pretentious English", they can just speak in one full English sentence, not just English prefixes or words. They can also learn pronunciation by using complete and correct sentences, not just "pretentious English" or "pretentious". This also applies to other languages, not just English. This is in line with Law No. 24/2009 that Indonesian serves as the nation's identity, national pride, a means of unifying various ethnic groups, as well as a means of communication between regions and between regional cultures. This is also written in the third youth oath, "We, the sons and daughters of Indonesia, uphold the language of unity, Indonesian." The oath implies that as the young generation of Indonesia, they are obliged to love, preserve, and uphold the Indonesian language as the language of unity, national language, and state language of Indonesia. This is a form of love for the Indonesian homeland.

DISCUSSION

From the results of the interviews above, it can be concluded that the majority of Indonesian people do not understand Presidential Regulation Number 63 of 2019 concerning the use of Indonesian, which says that the use of Indonesian must meet the criteria of good and correct Indonesian, namely Indonesian which is used in accordance with the language context and in harmony with the social values of the community which is in accordance with the rules of Indonesian language which are grammar rules, spelling rules and rules for forming terms. The use of mixed language has 2 impacts, namely positive and negative, the negative impact of using mixed language in daily conversation can reduce the existence of Indonesian, there will be many teenagers who increasingly do not know how good and correct Indonesian should be used in accordance with Indonesian language rules. Another impact of using mixed languages is that the use of mixed languages can make it difficult to use Indonesian properly and correctly. Even though at school or at work, we are required to always use good and correct language. Mixed language can disturb anyone who reads and hears the words included in it. Because not everyone understands what the words mean. Moreover, in written form, it is very confusing and requires more time to understand. The positive impact of using mixed languages is that it can hone skills and confidence in mastering foreign languages. As Indonesian citizens, we must preserve what has been intended by our ancestors and it is absolute that our daily language is Indonesian. Awareness from the community, especially Indonesian people as users of Indonesian, in using Indonesian. People should be wiser in sorting out the good and bad language they hear on the internet or other media so that they can limit the excessive use of mixed language.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Many cultures are mixed with modern culture. This mixed culture is difficult to distinguish from Indonesia's indigenous culture. The emergence of new cultures resulting from this mixed culture is sometimes difficult to understand and quite surprising. The most important culture is language. In the era of globalization, many languages are mixed and people are comfortable using these languages. Languages and cultures do not exist independently but are always influenced by other languages and cultures. other languages and cultures. Languages and cultures therefore constantly change, both due to their internal relationships with the social groups they form and their interactions with other languages and cultures. They form groups through interaction with other languages and cultures. other languages and cultures.

In this context, it cannot be denied that it is currently almost impossible to find a language that is completely unchanged. There are very few languages that are not influenced by other languages. Language is one of the most important elements of culture. As an element of culture, language can represent social changes occurring among its users. is in the midst of a user community. The dynamics of language users can be used as an indicator of the superiority of a particular culture over other cultures in a society. in society.

Language change and language development can occur both internally and externally. This article examines language change and development based on the history of language development and examines language change and internal development based on historical research. However, sociolinguistic research takes into account external change and development by studying and observing the change and development of language under the influence of sociocultural factors in society. Internal changes first appeared in the speaker's behavior in daily life. As we continue to adapt to each other, our tendency to innovate within our familiar social groups continues, leading to a chain reaction of further changes, eventually leading to the development of languages that, despite originally being from the same language family, continue to innovate within our familiar social groups. Languages became different from each other. Extralinguistic change is the change and development of a language resulting from contact with another language, whereby people change as cultural and social beings, both between nations in the world and among ethnic groups within countries interact with each other exchanged.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

It is hoped that in the future this research can be a reference for further in-depth research with the mixed method to get the accuracy of data and the significance of the relationship between variables that can be a reference for generation z behavior and approach patterns for generation z.

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